

Table 6.3: Participants' transcriptions of the guide's strengths.

Strengths	Transcriptions
Easy to understand and clear	<p>"This innovative approach facilitates the assimilation of content, making learning more dynamic and effective."</p> <p>"Easy visualization of information, access to information and wide range of consultation sources."</p> <p>"Access, easy language and no use of technical terms that make it difficult to understand."</p>
Applicability	<p>"These strategies help organizations ensure legal compliance and promote a culture of data protection."</p> <p>"By directly addressing the difficulties that organizations encounter, such as budget constraints and legal ambiguities, the guide becomes a relevant and applicable tool in the daily lives of work teams."</p> <p>"The strengths of a privacy compliance guide are: [...] flexibility to adapt, continuous training of employees."</p> <p>"The inclusion of an interactive game, which allows users to explore privacy guidelines in a playful way, not only</p>
Interactivity	<p>engages participants, but also promotes a deeper understanding of how different frameworks can meet legal requirements."</p> <p>"I liked the way the information was presented and the way it interacted with the Principles and Rights tabs."</p> <p>"The possibility of using the cards to select the ISO privacy principles."</p> <p>"The guide emphasizes education and awareness of privacy, promoting a responsible organizational culture in relation to data protection."</p>
Raising awareness	<p>"The strengths of a private compliance guide include: [...] Focus on employee education and awareness."</p> <p>"It helps to spread the importance of privacy."</p> <p>"It makes it easy to navigate privacy regulations."</p> <p>"Clear, direct, concise and allows you to quickly compare existing legislation in other countries."</p> <p>"The idea of the guide is excellent because it summarizes</p>
Simplified Access	<p>information on the main regulations on the subject in a single place."</p>

Table 6.4: Participants' transcriptions of the guide's strengths.

Weaknesses and improvements	Transcripts
Complexity for beginners	<p>"The user's need to understand the differences between countries' laws."</p> <p>"I believe that some of the information could be structured in such a way as to emphasize the LGPD as a starting point."</p> <p>"The guide also assumes a basic understanding of legal and technical terms, which can be a barrier for non-experts."</p> <p>"There's no option for Portuguese, since it involves the use</p>
Language in Portuguese	<p>of Brazilian regulations."</p> <p>"It could have been translated into Portuguese."</p> <p>"As it was a survey applied in Brazil and is also based on the LGPD, I missed the fact that it was available in Portuguese."</p>
Generalization	<p>"Generic approach, lacks customization for different types of organizations."</p> <p>"Generic approach, without considering specific needs." "The difficulty of serving all the bodies."</p>
Exemplification	<p>"Include practical real-world examples and case studies on how organizations overcome challenges."</p> <p>"[...] inclusion of practical examples and case studies."</p> <p>"Exemplify/practice."</p>